

The impact of HPTED on health levels by mediating physical activity of residents and the moderation role of perceived green space and perceived crime in a crime-ridden environment

Ali Montazeri

Department of Architecture, Islamic Azad University,
Ayatollah Amoli Branch, Amol, Iran

October 2025

Abstract

Maintaining and promoting physical and mental health (especially in crime-ridden cities) is a key factor in improving the quality of urban life. The present study addressed mechanical, geographical, methodological, experimental, and temporal gaps, presents a conceptual model based on an interdisciplinary approach between urban science, criminology, environmental psychology, and public health. adopting a post-positivist paradigm and a quantitative approach, this study collected data from 670 participants residing in the most crime-ridden districts of Tehran (recognized as the most crime-affected city in Iran) and employed variance-based structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) to examine the effect of HPTED principles on health through the mediating role of physical activity. The findings revealed that HPTED principles had a significant positive effect on both health and physical activity, with physical activity serving as a partial mediator. Perceived crime had a negative moderating effect on the effects of HPTED principles, and the perceived moderating effect of green space was not significant, indicating that although HPTED principles encourage physical participation and health improvement, perceived insecurity can overshadow it. Also, the MGA analysis shows a significant difference in the "length of residence (more or less than 10 years)" in the relationship between HPTED principles and physical activity,

and the moderating effect of perceived crime on it. The results of this study can be used as evidence-based guidance for policymakers and urban planners and provide a new perspective for improving the health of residents, especially in crime-prone areas..

Keywords: : HPTED, Physical activity, Health, Crime-prone, urban health, Structural equation modeling

1 Introduction

Urban development and machine life today have a dual function [Zhong et al., 2022]. While in its bright half, relying on machines [Dzewaltowski, 2008], robots and artificial intelligence [Abeliansky et al., 2024] reduced mobility and humans with less physical fatigue, store more energy and have higher efficiency [Farrahi and Clare, 2024], in the dark half, this decreases physical and mental mobility and constant reliance on technology. In addition to creating a consumer mindset, it also endangers their health [Hoare et al., 2016]. Living in environments that focus on machine life away instead of the natural parameters of an environment is one of the most important factors affecting the decline in health level [Squillacioti et al., 2023]. On the other hand, the environments that experience poorer health also report higher crime levels [Sampson, 2003]. In other words, the more individuals distance themselves from activities on both microscales (such as everyday tasks) and macroscales (such as social presence and participation), the more they limit their safe environment and, in a way, limit their own territory [Moyano-Diaz and Mendoza-Llanos, 2021]. This pervasive crisis, which perpetuates itself in an endless cycle of cause and effect, is not confined to any specific geographical location [WHO, 2010]; rather, it has become an interdisciplinary concern that has preoccupied scholars and planners for many years [Krug et al., 2002]. In response to this concern, the researchers, through a fundamental paradigm and theory that has been based on several interconnected disciplines, have proposed the CPTED theory in previous decades [Jeffery, 1971]. This theory, which consists of different dimensions and has evolved over the years, was focused on environmental design that would create a higher quality of life for residents, strengthening territoriality and reducing crime through environmental design [Cozens et al., 2005]. Although CPTED, throughout its evolution and across its various generations [Cozens and Love, 2015, Armitage, 2013, Wen et al., 2025], has made significant contributions to the advancement and development of solutions to this concern [Rupp

et al., 2025], in today's mechanized world, the rapid pace of urbanization and technological progress is surpassing the cultural capacity to properly utilize them [Andalib et al., 2024, Salmi et al., 2024]. Under such circumstances, concerns are no longer limited to protecting and enhancing safety against external threats and offenders that endanger physical and mental well-being, and other factors, such as physical inactivity and insufficient exercise [Guthold et al., 2018, Owen et al., 2010, Zhang et al., 2024], excessive dependence on technology, and the dominance of a mechanized lifestyle, have also emerged as potential sources of harm [Ghorbany et al., 2025, Przybylski and Weinstein, 2017]. These factors, which have limited the opportunity for movement and strengthening the physical and mental dimensions of humans due to their attractiveness, ease of use, and increasing expansion, have necessitated the existence of other principles that change lifestyles and another dimension of protection that leads to increased physical and mental security. This is something that in recent years, in the form of a multi-parameter theory called HPTED, is trying to create a better tomorrow for humans than today by designing in a way that increases human health.

Urban design that promotes health is not limited to one approach and one theorist [Karaan et al., 2024], many studies have taken steps to theoretically examine this concept and introduced different parameters [Kellert et al., 2008, Khalili et al., 2024, Matthews et al., 2024, Ruijsbroek et al., 2016, Seraphim et al., 2025]. However, as lifestyles are changing [Lan and Jin, 2025], our definition of health and the factors that influence it are also changing [Huang et al., 2024, Matta et al., 2024]. In urban design science, the HPTED theory was stated to be based on eight main pillars, including: Design in Collaboration (using user ideas and opinions in the design process), Design in Response to Context (paying attention to the site and respecting the identity of the area in order to adapt to the culture of the users), Design for Physical Activity (designing green space and walking and cycling paths to the extent that they invite residents to use them as much as possible and strive to reduce the use of motorized vehicles), Design for Social Cohesion and Equity (designing public spaces with equal access that, by increasing the presence of observers, in addition to increasing social interactions, reduce the potential for crime), Design for Access to Healthy Food (facilitating fair and easy access to healthy food sources in order to promote health and prevent diseases), Design for a Healthy Biophysical Environment (using drains and sewage disposal routes and preventing the accumulation of waste), Design for Safety and Security (using artificial factors (CCTV cameras) and natural factors (guards) to improve the security of residents), Design for Healthy and Affordable Housing (the availability of housing at different rates It is based on the possibility of buying for every budget category) [Kent and

Wheeler, 2016]. However, HPTED is merely a theory and principles for creating the conditions necessary to promote health but to link HPTED to the core concern, which is human health, it requires a connecting bridge. Physical activity, which is regarded as a solution of the principles of HPTED, can serve as that bridge [Boakye et al., 2023]. In fact, physical activity can put the HPTED theory into action and take steps towards increasing the health level of citizens [Montazeri, 2019]. However, what is important is the reality of a society, considering that HPTED is a continuation of CPTED [Hedayati Marzbali et al., 2019] and CPTED focuses on design to prevent crime [Atlas, 2008, Mihinjac and Saville, 2019], other factors must also be considered. For example, more physical activity means more connection with the surrounding environment [Wang et al., 2023], and in areas that report higher crime levels, CPTED and HPTED approaches are more needed and physical activity is not easily implemented there (Roman et al., 2024). Although according to the principles of CPTED, with increased participation and observing eyes, the level of crime will gradually decrease [Lee et al., 2016]. However, at the beginning and start of this movement, it should be kept in mind that factors such as perceived crime can affect the theoretical effects of HPTED, which is trying to be implemented using physical activity [Foster and Giles-Corti, 2008]. Perceived crime can also affect the impact of the parameters defined by HPTED on health [Mendes et al., 2014]. Crime and lawlessness can greatly affect an environment socially (preventing participation and social cohesion) [Tamura et al., 2020], environmentally (waste and pollution of the area) [Jonescu et al., 2024], psychologically (mugging and creating fear of victimization for residents) [Foster et al., 2016], culturally (prevalence of crime culture and street gangs) [Owusu et al., 2015], and even economically (vandalism and destruction of physical resources of the area) [Cysek-Pawlak et al., 2025], etc. On the other hand, in the half-light, we can point out the impact of environmental factors and their impact and encourage residents of an area to be present in the community or natural environments. Many studies have pointed out the impact of being in nature and the impact of trees, plants, and green spaces on mental and physical health [Russo, 2024, Rifas-Shiman et al., 2025, Refisch et al., 2024]. This can, in addition to increasing the desire for physical activity in public environments, also ensure a higher level of health by increasing this occurrence [Delgado-Serrano et al., 2024].

The evolution of existing knowledge reflects different perspectives and differences in attitudes towards a single goal, which is health (both physical and mental) through urban science [Singleton et al., 2023, Stappers et al., 2023, Zhong et al., 2022]. Decades of research and theory, from Antonovsky's salutogenic model in the late 1980s, which shifted the focus from pathology

to health promotion [Antonovsky, 1980], to Barton and Tsourou, who in the early part of this century sought to demonstrate a systematic relationship between urban planning and public health [Barton and Tsourou, 2000], and Sallis, who demonstrated the impact of the environment on increasing physical activity and reducing obesity with social-ecological models [Sallis et al., 2006]. A path that evolved with the second [Saville and Cleveland, 1997] and third generations of CPTED [Mihinjac and Saville, 2019], biophilic design [Kellert et al., 2008] and HPTED [Kent and Wheeler, 2016], and empirical research in the years that followed [Gianfredi et al., 2021, Putrik et al., 2019, Rigolon et al., 2021, Ruijsbroek et al., 2017], research that emphasizes direct relationships between the variables of the present study and their importance on the general health of individuals in a society.

Table 1: Literature background

Authors and year	Focus / Contribution	Key Findings	Methodology	Limitations
[Antonovsky, 1980]	Introduced the Salutogenic Model of Health, shifting focus from disease to well-being through Sense of Coherence (SOC).	Individuals with stronger SOC show better resilience and coping. Health is viewed as a dynamic balance of stress and resources.	Conceptual synthesis from sociology, psychology, and epidemiology.	Mainly theoretical; SOC operationalized later (1987).
[Saville and Cleveland, 1997]	Proposed 2nd Generation CPTED, adding social and psychological dimensions to physical design for crime prevention.	Community cohesion and resident participation are essential for sustainable safety.	Conceptual synthesis of CPTED and social ecology; case reflections.	Not empirically tested; limited operational strategies.
[Barton and Tsourou, 2000]	Linked urban planning with public health via the WHO Healthy Cities initiative (Healthy Urban Planning).	Compact, mixed-use, pedestrian design promotes activity and social equity.	Policy synthesis and European case studies.	Europe-focused; limited generalizability.
[Sallis et al., 2006]	Developed an ecological model integrating social, environmental, and policy levels of physical activity.	Built environment and policy factors are crucial for active living.	Comprehensive conceptual synthesis from multiple disciplines.	Mostly cross-sectional evidence; limited population diversity.
[Kellert et al., 2008]	Expanded biophilia theory to architecture via Biophilic Design and Restorative Environmental Design (RED).	Natural exposure enhances health, productivity, and recovery; six biophilic elements have been identified.	Interdisciplinary theoretical and empirical synthesis.	Conceptual, not experimental; lack of standard measures.

(continued on next page)

(continued from previous page)

Authors and year	Focus / Contribution	Key Findings	Methodology	Limitations
[Kent and Wheeler, 2016]	Introduced HPTED (Health Promotion Through Environmental Design) inspired by CPTED principles.	Promotes collaboration, social cohesion, safety, and healthy environments.	Conceptual comparative review of CPTED and health planning literature.	Lacks empirical validation; measurement challenges.
[Van den Bosch, 2016]	Comprehensive review linking urban green spaces with health outcomes (physical, mental, social).	3UGS improves activity, stress, and cohesion; the strongest evidence for mental health and PA.	Narrative synthesis of 200+ studies (Europe).	Europe focus; causality uncertain.
[Mihinjac and Saville, 2019]	Proposed 3rd Generation CPTED integrating sustainability, livability, and health.	Greening and health-focused design reduce crime and enhance well-being.	Theoretical synthesis from CPTED, liveability, and public health literature.	Conceptual; lacks empirical validation.
[Zhong et al., 2022]	Synthesized global studies on built environment–health relationships (1995–2022).	Compact, walkable environments increase PA and reduce obesity; crime affects well-being.	Systematic review with bibliometric and multi-level synthesis.	Review limited to English-language, indexed literature; limited empirical testing.
[Stappers et al., 2023]	Evaluated 6-year urban redesign effects on PA, sedentary behavior, and HRQoL (Green Carpet, NL).	Infrastructure reduced sedentary behavior, improved transport PA; HRQoL mixed.	Longitudinal natural experiment with accelerometer and GPS data.	Single-city study; COVID confounding; no randomization.
[Singleton et al., 2023]	Explored spatial links between violent crime, inactivity, and obesity across Chicago by race/ethnicity.	Crime positively correlated with inactivity/obesity, especially in Black and Hispanic tracts.	Spatial regression (OLS, SEM) using census-tract data.	Cross-sectional; limited generalizability.

In this regard, the HPTED principles, with an emphasis on the importance of physical activities, have a significant impact on increasing physical activity [Kent and Wheeler, 2016], which, in addition to the H1 hypothesis, according to the theories outlined in the table (1), can promote both physical and mental health, which is aligned with hypotheses H2 and H3 [Zhu et al., 2024]. On the other hand, to better understand an urban environment as well as external factors affecting it, we need to consider urban elements such as green spaces, as well as sociological parameters such as the amount of crime that can affect any environment and society that has it, and affect the physical and mental health of the residents, an issue that emphasizes the moderating effects of these two factors and can be seen in the conceptual model of the research as hypotheses H4 [Loh et al., 2019], H5 [Richardson et al., 2017, Zeng et al., 2022] and H6 Putman et al. [2023], Zhang et al. [2018].

Based on the theoretical literature and the format of the theoretical frame-

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

work of the research, part of which can be seen in Table 1, the conceptual model of the present research was developed, and the assumptions were created in the form of relevant propositions.

- H1: HPTED affect physical activity.
- H2: HPTED affect health.
- H3: Physical activity affects health.
- H4: Perceived crime influences the causal relationship between HPTED principles and physical activity.
- H5: Perceived crime influences the causal relationship between HPTED principles and Health.
- H6: Perceived green space influences the causal relationship between HPTED principles and Health.

Despite the existence of research with different and powerful perspectives and attitudes that have taken steps to address a wide range of needs, our understanding of urban design in a way that, in addition to physical

health, mental health and its full dimensions, including autonomy, competence, and relatedness [Bjornsen et al., 2017], considering all the factors of social influence in reality of one society and examine them at the same time, is superficial and incomplete [Prince et al., 2025]. Because these science-filled warehouses rarely meet by engaging all the dimensions mentioned in the research. These empty spots create interconnected gaps that require an innovative perspective to fill. The perspective adopted in this study is the design of a consolidated conceptual model to address the gaps identified in Table 2, fill them, and take a step forward in the evolution of this science.

Table 2: Research gap

Gap	Evidence in Literature and Limitations	Coverage in the present research
Mechanism	The major research aimed to determine whether urban components impact the health level of residents. Or how much physical activity can affect health [Althoff et al., 2024, Qin et al., 2025].	The current research does not seek to answer past questions, but seeks to prove how HPTED principles affect Health by mediating physical activity and the moderating role of green space and perceived crime based on the reality of a society.
Geographical	Most health studies have been conducted from the perspective of urban science and HPTED principles in developed countries, and samples from developing countries are almost absent [Kent and Wheeler, 2016].	The present study was conducted in Tehran as the capital of a developing country with a different cultural context, and by providing empirical evidence from a less studied context, it helps to fill the geographical gap present in the literature.
Methodological	The influence of health from the perspective of HPTED principles has been conceptual in nature and has been evaluated solely at the theoretical level or through a review of the literature [Hedayati Marzbali et al., 2019].	The present study, adopting a post-positivist paradigm and employing structural equation modeling, examined the concept of the health construct (both mental and physical dimensions) from the perspective of HPTED principles and physical activity, while considering variables with different roles, including independent, mediating, and moderating factors.
Empirical	To date, HPTED has primarily been examined from a conceptual perspective, with no empirical research published to test its theoretical assumptions.	The present study, for the first time, tested health from the perspective of HPTED principles in the form of a quantitative and empirical framework, thereby moving beyond a purely theoretical level.
Temporal	After the introduction of HPTED and its goal in promoting health in 2016, only one study looked at its concept in 2019, and no research has been published in recent years [Hedayati Marzbali et al., 2019, Kent and Wheeler, 2016].	For the first time since 2019, the study evaluates the role of HPTED principles in health.

In general, the current research has been trying to re-energize the energy, turning the eyes back to the impact of HPTED on health, and also passing through the conceptual stage with quantitative tests and entering the experimental stages in a developing country. Using an innovative and interdisciplinary combination and benefiting from different theories during the evolution of urban science, this research has helped to fill several gaps in the literature with advanced modeling, relying on the post-positivist paradigm and the use of an adequately powered sample, and considering demographic variables of identity. Achievements that, in addition to the evolution of this research process over the past decades, underlie future research and provide answers to questions that have not yet been asked.

The selection of Tehran and the chosen study districts as the setting for data collection was not random. Tehran is known as the most crime-ridden city of Iran [NUMBEO, 2025], and the data were collected from the city's most crime-affected districts (15, 12, 16, and 18) [Momeni and Irankhah, 2020]. This criminality, in addition to aligning with the perceived crime variable and paying attention to the important and influential components of urban science, is also in line with the main concern of CPTED principles and provides a serious and vital test to evaluate the HPTED principles and their impact on the health level of residents of a region. A theme that, with the mediation of physical activity in the form of a bridge-binding, insists on the relationship between the principles of HPTED and health, in addition to promoting health by increasing physical metabolism [Speakman and Selman, 2003], it also functions within the framework of increasing "eyes on the street," which is another component of CPTED [Brown et al., 2008]. Understanding how and whether HPTED principles can affect health through physical activity is important not only for Iran's domestic policymaking as a developing country, but also for understanding the performance of the above on all crime-ridden and even non-crime-ridden areas. In fact, the choice of the crime zone itself applies a moderating effect on the entire research model and the assumptions raised, and examines all the frameworks set out most difficultly. The findings of this study can serve as a guiding light for a wide range of audiences from academics to practitioners in urban studies, policymaking, and planning, as well as sociologists, environmental psychologists, and even public health professionals, helping them, through the understanding of these findings and the empirical evidence presented for the first time, gain a more comprehensive insight into the theoretical and conceptual research previously discussed.

2 Methodology

The present study was conducted between October 2023 and June 2024 within the framework of the post-positivism paradigm and using a quantitative approach [Vega, 2022]. The research data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics and using various validity and reliability techniques. Variance-based structural equation modeling was chosen to test the hypotheses due to the presence of formative measurement instruments [Corry et al., 2019, Hauff et al., 2025].

2.1 Population and Sample

The target population of this study includes all citizens living in urban environments exposed to crime, delinquency, and social harm concerns, which is a common and universal challenge in contemporary societies. The accessible population consisted of individuals aged 18 and above who resided in Tehran (the most crime-ridden city in Iran) and specifically in the districts with the highest crime rates (Districts 15, 12, 16, and 18). To determine the required sample size, Cohen's effect size formula was used. In this calculation, an effect size of 0.2, a confidence level of 99%, and a statistical power of 0.85 were considered, resulting in a minimum required sample size of 632 participants. To enhance precision, generalizability, and account for potential non-responses or exclusions, the sample size was increased by approximately 10% to 690 participants. Data were collected in the field using a structured questionnaire in the selected districts.

2.2 Measurement tools

Reflective and composite questionnaires were used to measure the research variables. The indicators of mental health (autonomy, competence, relatedness) [Bjornsen et al., 2017], physical health [Shi et al., 2022], perceived green space [Sugiyama et al., 2010], and physical activity [Cho, 2016] were extracted from pre-tested sources, and the indicators related to the variables of perceived crime [of Iran, 2021] and HPTED [Kent and Wheeler, 2016] are being tested for the first time. The questions related to perceived crime were developed with consideration of the differences between reported and officially recorded crimes in Iran compared to other regions, and were based on available official sources. For example, crimes such as sexual assault are not recorded in the judicial statistical yearbooks in Iran, making it impossible

to use some existing sources or questionnaires that include this component. However, components such as murder and suicide (unnatural deaths), individual and group conflicts, assault (including robbery), theft (residential, commercial, vehicular, etc.), and drug trafficking are included in the judicial yearbooks. Since the most recent edition of this yearbook corresponds to 2021, the recorded components from that edition were used. Regarding the HPTED variable, eight principles were identified, each sufficiently abstract to allow for its own dimension and specific questions. However, because no previous study has operationalized these principles, and using multiple separate sources that individually address each principle could bias the author's intended interpretation of them, each principle was formulated as a single question. These questions were fully explained to respondents in line with the ideology and thinking of Kent and Wheeler, ensuring fidelity to the content of the original principles. All items (except physical activity) were rated using a 5-point Likert scale, from 1= "very low" to 5 = "very high". The response options for physical activity's questionnaire were as follows: Question 1: (What type of physical activity are you doing?) 1= sedentary activity, 2= performing arts & crafts, 3= performing one type of physical activity among them, 4= performing two types of physical activity among CE, RE, FE, 5= performing all types of CE, RE, FE; Question 2: (During a week, how often do you participate in the activity in your free time?) 1= sometimes, 2= 1-2 days/week, 3= 3 days/week, 4= 4-5 days/week, 5= almost every day; Question 3: (How intensely do you participate in the activity?) 1= very light, 2= light, 3= moderate, 4= hard, 5= very hard; Question 4: (How long do you do the activity in your free time?) 1= less than 30 minutes, 2= 30-60 minutes, 3= 60-90 minutes, 4= 90-120 minutes, 5= more than 120 minutes; and Question 5: (How monthly have you been performing the activity?) 1= less than 1 month, 2= 1-2 months, 3= 3-4 months, 4= 5-6 months, 5= more than 5 months.

3 Results

The researcher collected 690 data (632 + 10%) using the distribution of questionnaires in the mentioned districts of Tehran. Initially, the raw data were screened using SPSS 20 software, and after removing irrelevant data (see Appendix), 670 clean and analyzable cases remained (see Appendix). These data were then examined through descriptive statistics presented in Table 3 and inferential analyses, including hypothesis testing, mediation, and MGA [F. Hair Jr et al., 2014].

Table 3: The demographic profile of respondents

	Variable	Frequency	%
Gender	Male	407	60.7
	Female	263	39.3
District	15	165	24.6
	12	168	25.1
	16	171	25.5
	18	166	24.8
Length of residence (Year)	Less than 10	221	33.0
	More than 10	449	67
Age	18-35	273	40.7
	36-55	226	33.7
	Above 55	171	25.5
Educationr	Less than Diploma	104	15.5
	Diploma and less	284	42.4
	Bachelor and less	354	52.8
	Master's AND above	32	4.8

3.1 Inferential statistics

For inferential statistics analysis, validity, reliability, model quality, hypotheses, mediator analysis, and qualitative moderator were examined. Given the presence of a variable with formative indicators, variance-based structural equation modeling, and SmartPLS software as employed [Moradi and Miralmasi]. The initial outer model (see Appendix) showed us that the reflective indicators (PH 1/ P.C 2) have outer loadings below 0.7, and the formative indicators (HPTED2 / HPTED6 / HPTED8) showed non-significant weight coefficients and should be removed from the outer model due to the lack of two necessary conditions of homogeneity [Sarstedt et al., 2017] (see Appendix).

Before conducting the inner model tests, it is essential to ensure the validity, reliability, and quality of the variables. Therefore, Cronbach's alpha and McDonald's omega tests were applied, with the threshold values greater than 0.7 [Fu et al., 2022]. Additionally, the AVE test requires values above 0.5, and the rho_c and rho_a coefficients are expected to exceed the AVE value (see Table 4) to confirm convergent validity between the indicators of reflective variables [Zhu et al., 2025].

Table 4: Construct reliability and validity

Latent Variable	α (pls)	ω (spss)	rho_a	rho_c	AVE
Autonomy	0.792	0.813	0.816	0.878	0.706
Competence	0.723	0.742	0.779	0.841	0.640
Relatedness	0.735	0.728	0.742	0.833	0.555
Perceived Crime	0.827	0.813	0.866	0.873	0.633
Perceived Green Space	0.897	0.876	0.912	0.924	0.710
Physical Activity	0.896	0.901	0.923	0.923	0.707
Physical Health	0.867	0.879	0.874	0.910	0.718

To calculate the divergent validity between the reflective variable indicators, the Fornell-Larker and Cross-Loading tests were used, and it was found that each index only measured its desired variable [Fornell and Larcker, 1981]. In Table 5, the divergent validity of current variables of research is observed with the HTMT test, where a coefficient less than 0.9 of each indicator indicates the absence of multicollinearity among the research variables [Roemer et al., 2021].

Table 5: HTMT

	Aut	Com	P.C	P.G.S	P.A	P.H	Rel
Aut							
Com	0.537						
P.C	0.078	0.106					
P.G.S	0.074	0.125	0.091				
P.A	0.150	0.358	0.211	0.140			
P.H	0.221	0.333	0.312	0.258	0.540		
Rel	0.479	0.432	0.072	0.067	0.108	0.092	

In the next stage, the quality assessment of both the outer and inner models was conducted. For this purpose, PLSPredict and RMSE and MAE indicators were applied [F. Hair Jr et al., 2014].

Figure 2: Inner model

Table 6: Quality indicators of Inner Model (LV)

	RMSE	MAE
Autonomy	1.015	0.858
Competence	0.979	0.827
Relatedness	1.049	0.892
Physical Activity	0.733	0.609
Physical Health	0.822	0.708

Note: RMSE > MAE

3.2 Inner model

After evaluating the quality of the outer model (see Appendix) and the inner model (Table 6), the analysis proceeded to the inner model to test the hypotheses and assess the predictive accuracy [Hair et al., 2022].

The results of the internal model of the research show that in the first equation, the HPTED variable has a significant effect on physical activity ($\beta = 0.651$) at the 99% confidence level ($P < 0.05$). Considering the coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.481$), the explanatory power of the model is evaluated as moderate according to Chin's criteria [Marcoulides, 2013]. However, given that this equation includes only one independent variable,

Table 7: Hypothesis

Hypothesis	Latent Variable	β	VIF	T value	P value	Result
H1	HPTED \rightarrow Physical Activity	0.651	1.113	24.689	0.000	confirmed
H2	HPTED \rightarrow Health	0.275	1.942	4.792	0.000	confirmed
H3	Physical Activity \rightarrow Health	0.220	1.944	4.690	0.000	confirmed
H4*	P.C * HPTED \rightarrow Physical Activity	-0.216	1.014	8.150	0.000	confirmed
H5*	P.C * HPTED \rightarrow Health	-0.075	1.107	2.523	0.000	confirmed
H6*	P.G.S* Physical Activity \rightarrow Health	0.022	1.032	0.808	0.419	Rejected

Notes: * = Interaction moderator

the R^2 value of 0.481 is notably substantial. In the second equation (Hypotheses 2 and 3), the effects of HPTED ($\beta = 0.275$) and physical activity ($\beta = 0.220$) on the overall health variable were found to be significant at the 99% confidence level ($P < 0.05$). Considering the coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.286$), the explanatory power of the model is classified as weak according to Chin's effect size criteria. However, given the complex and multifactorial nature of health-related behaviors and dimensions in the fields of social and urban sciences, as well as the number of influencing variables in this equation, the R^2 value of 0.286 is considered acceptable. In the fourth hypothesis, the moderating effect of perceived crime on the H1 hypothesis (HPTED principles on physical activity) is significant with a 99% confidence level, according to $P < 0.05$, and according to the coefficient $\beta = -0.216$, the findings indicate a negative moderating effect of perceived crime. In the fifth hypothesis, which examines the moderating effect of perceived crime on the H2 hypothesis (HPTED principles on health), $P < 0.05$ is significant with a 99% confidence level, and according to the coefficient $\beta = -0.075$, the effect is negative but weaker compared to Hypothesis 4. Finally, in the sixth hypothesis, perceived green space plays a moderating role on the third hypothesis (physical activity on health). However, since the hypothesis was not supported ($P = 0.419$), this moderating relationship was found to be statistically insignificant.

3.3 Mediation analysis

The presence of mediating and moderating variables in the post-positivist paradigm brings the research's conceptual model to the reality of society [Magill, 2011]. According to the theoretical literature and the research model, physical activity serves as a mediating variable between HPTED and health.

According to Sobel (1986), who believes that mediation is a variable that passes the effect of the independent variable on the dependent either partially or completely [Woody, 2011]. Considering its robustness to distributional assumptions, reflective indicators, and sample size, the Sobel bootstrapping test was employed to examine the mediating effect [Moradi and Miralmasi].

Table 8: Mediation analysis

	a	b	c	axb	$(axb) + c$	VAF	Result
Physical Activity	0.651	0.220	0.275	0.143	0.418	0.342	Partial Mediator

Note: c = direct effect , axb = indirect effect, $(axb) + c$ = total effect , VIF = indirect effect/total effect

According to Table 8, which examines the mediating role of physical activity in the causal relationship between HPTED principles and health, the VAF coefficient was found to be 0.342. Based on the effect size range defined by Sobel ($0.02 \leq \text{VAF} \leq 0.8$), this value indicates a partial mediation effect.

3.4 Qualitative moderator (MGA)

Among the intricate analyses in structural equation modeling is the examination of demographic variables as qualitative moderators, which involves comparing multiple groups of one nominal or ordinal variable to determine whether the relationships proposed in each hypothesis differ across them [Montoya, 2019].

Table 9: MGA analysis

Variable	H1	H2	H3	H4	H5	H6
Length of residence	*					*

According to the results of the cross-group analysis, the first hypothesis (HPTED's effect on physical activity) and fourth (HPTED's perceived crime moderation on physical activity impact) report significant differences between two groups of residents who lived longer than 10 years and less than 10 years in the mentioned districts.

4 Discussion

The present study aimed to determine how HPTED principles affect the health of citizens of crime-ridden areas, with a focus on physical activity. The findings from the conceptual model of the research, such as the light, illuminated the path to understanding the increase in the health of residents of an area through environmental design, and revealed the positive, negative, and meaningful effects of the assumptions made. The findings highlight the importance of engaging in physical activity for health promotion and reveal, through a qualitative moderator, how the impact of physical activity by shaped with HPTED principles and perceived crime varies according to the length of residents' stay in high-crime areas.

The findings showed a positive effect of HPTED principles on increasing physical activity and health level, and the mediating and supporting role of physical activity in promoting health. In other words, an environment built on the principles of HPTED can increase the desire for physical activity, and increased physical activity, as well as HPTED principles, can lead to higher levels of mental and physical health. According to Table 7, HPTED principles alone can predict up to 48 percent of the level of physical activity and have a 65 percent impact on it. Given that this equation has only one independent variable, it can be argued that an environment designed according to the principles of HPTED can significantly increase the desire for physical activity of residents and take a major step towards increasing the level of health. In addition, in the next equation, where health (physical and mental) was evaluated by HPTED principles and physical activity, the findings indicate $R^2 = 0.29$, which can be appropriate for the predictive power of independent variables, given the number of predictive variables and the complexity of health level assessment. However, the interesting point of the second equation was the higher beta coefficient of the HPTED principles than physical activity. In the second equation, the principles of HPTED, with an impact of 0.275 on physical activity with an impact of 0.220, have been able to have a higher impact on health, which indicates the more effective role of the above principles in promoting health. Although physical activity and the partial mediator effect explain how HPTED principles can increase health, there are other factors in the environment that can affect health or physical activity by negatively affecting themselves. For example, in the fourth hypothesis, the perceived crime variable and its moderating effect on the first hypothesis (HPTED principles on physical activity) with modulatory power -0.216 can have a significant negative impact on the effectiveness of HPTED principles on physical activity, in other words, if residents of an area experience high levels of crime, even if the area is designed according to HPTED principles,

it overshadows and threatens the physical activity of residents. This effect is also true in the fifth hypothesis (the effect of HPTED principles on health), and perceived crime can have a negative impact on it. However, when we look at the power of influence, we find that the impact of perceived crime on the causal relationship of HPTED principles on health levels (-0.075) is much less than the causal relationship of HPTED principles on physical activity (-0.216). It can be argued that HPTED principles are potentially less influenced by external negative social factors, however, when they are applied in practice and involve a greater presence in public spaces, their susceptibility to such influences increases. As mentioned in the initial part of the research, though the HPTED principles, which are based on CPTED principles, are initially and when society is encouraged to attend to dynamic physical activity, use public transport, and, in other words, promote greater participation and social cohesion given the society's backgrounds (public crime or the limitations of women in communities in developing countries), it faces difficulties and when in the actual stage, the effectiveness of negative factors is more pronounced, but as CPTED has pointed out over time, and with increasing contributions and observer's eyes, and when participants believe they are able to participate in society without the threat of threatening and expanding their territory, their negative impact on perceived crime will also decrease. Another debatable topic was the qualitative moderator effect of "Length of residence" in the crime-ridden region, which was divided into two categories: less than 10 years and more than 10 years. Of the six hypotheses presented in this study, this qualitative moderator can report significant differences in the two H1 and H4 hypotheses. In other words, people who stayed longer in the area report a different impact on physical activity from the HPTED principles, and also the perceived crime moderator effect on the causal relationship of HPTED principles to physical activity. The findings of this analysis support the claim of the previous paragraph that, in the event of greater presence and development of the territory, residents can experience a different experience with less mental concern and an increase in the amount of physical activity, from the moderating effect of perceived crime. Many studies have been conducted on the promotion of health in urban science and environmental psychology, etc. However, research that looks at the empirical study of the principles of HPTED and its impact on physical activity and the health of citizens has not been done. The researcher uses the post-positivism paradigm and quantitative approach using a conceptual model consisting of variables with different roles: independent, mediator, moderator (interaction and qualitative), and dependent, examining all the direct and indirect effects acknowledged in the research literature. The research, which is testing HPTED principles experimentally for the first time,

examines how data extracted from the most criminogenic areas of Iran's most crime-ridden city, as a developing country, impacts the mental and physical health of residents through HPTED principles and physical activity. In fact, the selection of high-crime areas was a deliberate research strategy to examine the level of crime perceived by the inhabitants, which served as a moderating variable in the formulation of the conceptual model. This approach allowed the study to reflect real societal contexts and to assess the influence of HPTED principles on health under the most challenging circumstances. Additionally, using a sample of 670 participants and applying structural equation modeling enhanced the robustness of the findings and increased the generalizability of the results from the sample to the target population.

Based on the research background and findings from the literature, Hypotheses 1 and 2 (positive and significant effects of HPTED principles on physical activity and health) were supported [Kent and Wheeler, 2016]. This was also true for Hypothesis 3, which examined the effect of physical activity on health [Dore et al., 2019, Gebel et al., 2005, Jewett et al., 2014]. As expected, the moderating effect of perceived crime on the causal relationships between HPTED principles on both physical activity and health was significant and negative. In other words, although HPTED principles encourage residents to engage in physical activity and, ultimately, achieve higher health levels, perceived crime can significantly diminish the strength of this effect. According to the findings of the present study, this negative impact could be mitigated over the long term by applying CPTED and HPTED principles [Casteel and Peek-Asa, 2000]. However, the sixth hypothesis, which was the moderating effect of perceived green space on the causal relationship of physical activity on health, was not confirmed. Despite the literature of the research, which indicates the impact of perceived green space on the amount of physical activity and willingness of individuals to do activity in green environments, they are [Sugiyama et al., 2008, Takano et al., 2002], even considering that according to the latest per capita green space published in the official domestic news base, the areas studied (15-16-18, except 12) are in the upper half of the green space per capita table in Tehran [online, 2019], however, according to the average obtained response to indicators related to green space perceived by residents of the above areas We see very low scores in this section, which can have a variety of reasons. For example, the adequacy of the perceived green space by residents can be highlighted. In other words, although the amount of green space in the studied areas numerically and officially approaches the average of formal standards, it is not considered satisfactory by the residents, who express a need for more greenery. This issue may also have social roots. Factors such as poorly organized park lay-

outs, insufficient security personnel, and a lack of surveillance cameras can create secluded and unsupervised areas that provide favorable conditions for criminal activities. Field evidence indicates that in such spaces, offenders often engage in activities such as drug use and trafficking. Moreover, in parks located in economically disadvantaged neighborhoods, homeless individuals or rough sleepers are frequently found residing in corners of the park, further diminishing the perceived safety and desirability of these environments. Therefore, it can be concluded that despite the amount of green space close to the defined per capita average in Tehran, due to the presence of rough sleepers, addicts, and criminals. The green space available to residents, especially women, is much less than what is recorded in the numbers. The case that has led to the rejection of the moderating effect of perceived green space on the causal relationship between physical activity and health, which has been introduced in previous studies to be quite meaningful and influential [Mytton et al., 2012, Song et al., 2025, Wang et al., 2021], and according to the beta obtained in this hypothesis, even if confirmed, it will have a very partial impact on H3 (Physical activity on health).

Despite its insightful findings, the present study encountered several limitations. As explained in the Methodology section, the indicators of perceived crime and HPTED principles were tested for the first time. The perceived crime indicators were categorized based on official data obtained from the National Statistical Center of Iran. While, due to the unique social, political, and religious context of Iran, these classifications may differ from international crime reporting standards. Furthermore, each HPTED principle possessed the potential to constitute a separate analytical dimension, the research adhered to the original conceptual integrity of Kent and Wheeler's model. Consequently, the interviewer limited the additional explanations to brief clarifications offered to participants during the survey process. Due to the criminality and social conditions governing the environment, it was less possible for women to participate than men, and some questions of demographic variables such as marital status were not possible, which, after collecting approximately 30 questionnaires according to the conditions, were preferred that the marital variable was originally considered as one of the variables of the MGA test be removed from the questionnaire.

It is recommended that future researchers expand the model to include social and cultural dimensions in order to examine health (physical and mental) from a broader perspective of urban health-promoting factors. Moreover, given the absence of a comprehensive and standardized measurement tool for assessing HPTED principles, the development of such an instrument capable of capturing all relevant indicators is of considerable importance. Additionally, to gain a clearer understanding of the actual impact of HPTED

principles on health, it is suggested that similar studies be conducted in safer urban environments with lower reported crime rates, where equal participation is more feasible. Comparing the results obtained from such settings with those from crime-prone areas could offer a deeper understanding of possible hidden dimensions of this phenomenon. Under such conditions, the moderating effect of perceived green space on the relationship between physical activity and health also has the potential to become significant. Finally, the above steps in the community of a different sample of cultural and social types can prevent cultural biases that are likely to be present in the research and help improve the quality of subsequent research.

Finally, according to the conceptual model, which sought to predict the main goal of the research, the impact of HPTED on health was reported to be positive and meaningful, and physical activity also had a positive mediating and impacting role. Perceived green space was incapable of playing its moderating role, but perceived crime had a significant and reducing effect moderating effect on HPTED relationships on health and physical activity. It is hoped that, according to the results obtained and with the capabilities and facilities of the powerful fields and institutions, a useful and efficient step will be taken to improve the health of residents of all parts of the world, in crime-ridden and even safer areas.

Conclusions

The study highlights the importance of the role of HPTED principles on physical activity and their impact on health (physical and mental) of residents of crime-ridden areas, which is shared by all parts of the world, and points to the importance of paying attention to crime and perceived green space. Also, by examining demographic factors, the difference in effectiveness of the above is revealed in the Length of residence, or in other words, the sense of belonging that is caused by longer residence. The present study provides a new look at the concept of environmental health factors and suggests that urban institutions and policymakers use the capacity of HPTED principles and environmental planning, and by creating safer and health-oriented environments, take an effective step in improving the physical and mental health of citizens of crime-ridden areas and even safer areas.

Author note

The abstract of this paper was accepted for presentation at the Fifteenth International Conference on Health, Wellness & Society, Granada, Spain, 2025. However, due to personal reasons, the author was unable to attend the conference. Supplementary materials: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17488101>

Acknowledgements

The present article is an expanded version of the researcher's master's thesis (at Islamic Azad University, Ayatollah Amoli Branch in 2019), conducted with a new statistical population and sample size. It employs a more innovative and developed research model. The researcher benefited significantly from the guidance of his thesis advisors, Dr. Hedayati and Dr. Maghsodi, who offered invaluable advice and constructive suggestions, facilitating the research process. The researcher extends his gratitude and respect to the other two professors, Dr. Moradi and Dr. Miralmasi, whose contributions have greatly enhanced his abilities in statistical calculation and analysis.

Declaration of Interest

I declare that my research is independent and not influenced by external factors such as financial resources, personal or professional relationships, or political affiliations. This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

References

Ana Lucia Abeliensky, Matthias Beulmann, and Klaus Prettnner. Are they coming for us? Industrial robots and the mental health of workers. *Research Policy*, 53(3):104956, April 2024. ISSN 00487333. doi: 10.1016/j.respol.2024.104956. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0048733324000052>.

Tim Althoff, Boris Ivanovic, Jennifer L. Hicks, Scott L. Delp, Abby C. King, and Jure Leskovec. Countrywide natural experiment reveals impact of

- built environment on physical activity, 2024. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.04557>. Version Number: 1.
- Elham Andalib, Alenka Temeljotov-Salaj, Martin Steinert, Agnar Johansen, Pasi Aalto, and Jardar Lohne. The Interplay Between the Built Environment, Health, and Well-Being—A Scoping Review. *Urban Science*, 8(4): 184, October 2024. ISSN 2413-8851. doi: 10.3390/urbansci8040184. URL <https://www.mdpi.com/2413-8851/8/4/184>.
- Aaron Antonovsky. *Health, stress, and coping*. The Jossey-Bass social and behavioral science series. Jossey-Bass Publishers, San Francisco, 1st ed edition, 1980. ISBN 978-0-87589-412-6.
- Rachel Armitage. *Crime prevention through housing design: policy and practice*. Crime prevention and security management. Palgrave Macmillan, Basingstoke, 2013. ISBN 978-1-137-31605-9 978-0-230-35617-7. doi: 10.1057/9781137316059.
- Randall Atlas. *21st Century Security and CPTED: Designing for Critical Infrastructure Protection and Crime Prevention*. Auerbach Publications, May 2008. ISBN 978-1-4200-6807-8 978-1-4200-6808-5. doi: 10.1201/9781420068085. URL <http://www.crcnetbase.com/doi/book/10.1201/9781420068085>.
- Hugh Barton and Catherine Tsourou. *Healthy Urban Planning*. Taylor and Francis, Hoboken, 2000. ISBN 978-0-415-24326-1.
- Hanne Nissen Bjornsen, Mary-Elizabeth Bradley Eilertsen, Regine Ringdal, Geir Arild Espnes, and Unni Karin Moksnes. Positive mental health literacy: development and validation of a measure among Norwegian adolescents. *BMC Public Health*, 17(1):717, December 2017. ISSN 1471-2458. doi: 10.1186/s12889-017-4733-6. URL <http://bmcpublihealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12889-017-4733-6>.
- Kwadwo Boakye, Marit Bovbjerg, John Schuna, Adam Branscum, Ravi Prasad Varma, Rosnah Ismail, Olga Barbarash, Juan Dominguez, Yuksel Altuntas, Ranjit Mohan Anjana, Rita Yusuf, Roya Kelishadi, Patricio Lopez-Jaramillo, Romaina Iqbal, Pamela Seron, Annika Rosengren, Paul Poirier, P. V. M. Lakshmi, Rasha Khatib, Katarzyna Zaton-ska, Bo Hu, Lu Yin, Chuangshi Wang, Karen Yeates, Jephath Chifamba, Khalid F Alhabib, Alvaro Avezum, Antonio Dans, Scott A Lear, Salim Yusuf, and Perry Hystad. Urbanization and physical activity in the global Prospective Urban and Rural Epidemiology study. *Sci Rep*, 13(1):290,

- January 2023. ISSN 2045-2322. doi: 10.1038/s41598-022-26406-5. URL <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-022-26406-5>.
- Scott C. Brown, Craig A. Mason, Tatiana Perrino, Joanna L. Lombard, Frank Martinez, Elizabeth Plater-Zyberk, Arnold R. Spokane, and Jose Szapocznik. Built Environment and Physical Functioning in Hispanic Elders: The Role of “Eyes on the Street”. Environ Health Perspect, 116(10):1300–1307, October 2008. ISSN 0091-6765, 1552-9924. doi: 10.1289/ehp.11160. URL <https://ehp.niehs.nih.gov/doi/10.1289/ehp.11160>.
- Carri Casteel and Corinne Peek-Asa. Effectiveness of crime prevention through environmental design (CPTED) in reducing robberies. American Journal of Preventive Medicine, 18(4):99–115, May 2000. ISSN 07493797. doi: 10.1016/S0749-3797(00)00146-X. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S074937970000146X>.
- Min-Haeng Cho. Preliminary reliability of the five item physical activity questionnaire. J Phys Ther Sci, 28(12):3393–3397, 2016. ISSN 0915-5287, 2187-5626. doi: 10.1589/jpts.28.3393. URL https://www.jstage.jst.go.jp/article/jpts/28/12/28_jpts-2016-677/_article.
- Margarita Corry, Sam Porter, and Hugh McKenna. The redundancy of positivism as a paradigm for nursing research. Nursing Philosophy, 20(1): e12230, January 2019. ISSN 1466-7681, 1466-769X. doi: 10.1111/nup.12230. URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/nup.12230>.
- Paul Cozens and Terence Love. A Review and Current Status of Crime Prevention through Environmental Design (CPTED). Journal of Planning Literature, 30(4):393–412, November 2015. ISSN 0885-4122, 1552-6593. doi: 10.1177/0885412215595440. URL <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/0885412215595440>.
- Paul Michael Cozens, Greg Saville, and David Hillier. Crime prevention through environmental design (CPTED): a review and modern bibliography. Property Management, 23(5):328–356, December 2005. ISSN 0263-7472. doi: 10.1108/02637470510631483. URL <http://www.emerald.com/pm/article/23/5/328-356/323104>.
- Monika Maria Cysek-Pawlak, Aleksander Serafin, and Andrii Polishchuk. Safe and Sustainable City: Exploring the Impact of Urban Factors on Crime Occurrence. Sustainability, 17(5):1866, February 2025. ISSN

2071-1050. doi: 10.3390/su17051866. URL <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/17/5/1866>.

Maria Mar Delgado-Serrano, Katarina Melichova, Isotta Mac Fadden, and Catalina Cruz-Piedrahita. Perception of green spaces' role in enhancing mental health and mental well-being in small and medium-sized cities. Land Use Policy, 139:107087, April 2024. ISSN 02648377. doi: 10.1016/j.landusepol.2024.107087. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0264837724000395>.

Isabelle Dore, Catherine M. Sabiston, Marie-Pierre Sylvestre, Jennifer Brunet, Jennifer O'Loughlin, Patrick Abi Nader, François Gallant, and Mathieu Belanger. Years Participating in Sports During Childhood Predicts Mental Health in Adolescence: A 5-Year Longitudinal Study. Journal of Adolescent Health, 64(6):790–796, June 2019. ISSN 1054139X. doi: 10.1016/j.jadohealth.2018.11.024. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1054139X19300217>.

David A. Dzewaltowski. Emerging Technology, Physical Activity, and Sedentary Behavior. Exercise and Sport Sciences Reviews, 36(4):171–172, October 2008. ISSN 0091-6331. doi: 10.1097/JES.0b013e31818784ef. URL <https://journals.lww.com/00003677-200810000-00001>.

Joe F. Hair Jr, Marko Sarstedt, Lucas Hopkins, and Volker G. Kuppelwieser. Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM): An emerging tool in business research. European Business Review, 26(2):106–121, March 2014. ISSN 0955-534X. doi: 10.1108/EBR-10-2013-0128. URL <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/EBR-10-2013-0128/full/html>.

Vahid Farrahi and Philip Clare. Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning—Powerful Yet Underutilized Tools and Algorithms in Physical Activity and Sedentary Behavior Research. Journal of Physical Activity and Health, 21(4):320–322, April 2024. ISSN 1543-3080, 1543-5474. doi: 10.1123/jpah.2024-0021. URL <https://journals.humankinetics.com/view/journals/jpah/21/4/article-p320.xml>.

Claes Fornell and David F. Larcker. Evaluating Structural Equation Models with Unobservable Variables and Measurement Error. Journal of Marketing Research, 18(1):39, February 1981. ISSN 00222437. doi: 10.2307/3151312. URL <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3151312?origin=crossref>.

- Sarah Foster and Billie Giles-Corti. The built environment, neighborhood crime and constrained physical activity: An exploration of inconsistent findings. *Preventive Medicine*, 47(3):241–251, September 2008. ISSN 00917435. doi: 10.1016/j.ypmed.2008.03.017. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0091743508001588>.
- Sarah Foster, Paula Hooper, Matthew Knuiman, Hayley Christian, Fiona Bull, and Billie Giles-Corti. Safe RESIDential Environments? A longitudinal analysis of the influence of crime-related safety on walking. *Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act*, 13(1):22, December 2016. ISSN 1479-5868. doi: 10.1186/s12966-016-0343-4. URL <https://ijbnpa.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12966-016-0343-4>.
- Yuanshu Fu, Zhonglin Wen, and Yang Wang. A Comparison of Reliability Estimation Based on Confirmatory Factor Analysis and Exploratory Structural Equation Models. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 82(2):205–224, April 2022. ISSN 0013-1644, 1552-3888. doi: 10.1177/00131644211008953. URL <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/00131644211008953>.
- Klaus Gebel, Lesley King, Adrian E Bauman, philip vita, Tim Gill, Angela Rigby, and Adam Capon. *Creating healthy environments: a review of links between the physical environmen, physical activity and obesity*. NSW Centre for Overweight and Obesity, Sydney, 2005. ISBN 978-1-921186-00-4. OCLC: 225389784.
- Siavash Ghorbany, Ming Hu, Siyuan Yao, Matthew Sisk, Chaoli Wang, Kai Zhang, and Quynh Camthi Nguyen. Data driven assessment of built environment impacts on urban health across United States cities. *Sci Rep*, 15(1):19998, June 2025. ISSN 2045-2322. doi: 10.1038/s41598-025-04567-3. URL <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-025-04567-3>.
- Vincenza Gianfredi, Maddalena Buffoli, Andrea Rebecchi, Roberto Croci, Aurea Oradini-Alacreu, Giuseppe Stirparo, Alessio Marino, Anna Odone, Stefano Capolongo, and Carlo Signorelli. Association between Urban Greenspace and Health: A Systematic Review of Literature. *IJERPH*, 18(10):5137, May 2021. ISSN 1660-4601. doi: 10.3390/ijerph18105137. URL <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/18/10/5137>.
- Regina Guthold, Gretchen A Stevens, Leanne M Riley, and Fiona C Bull. Worldwide trends in insufficient physical activity from 2001 to 2016: a pooled analysis of 358 population-based surveys with 1.9 million participants. *The Lancet Global Health*, 6(10):e1077–e1086, October 2018.

ISSN 2214109X. doi: 10.1016/S2214-109X(18)30357-7. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S2214109X18303577>.

Joseph F. Hair, G. Tomas M. Hult, Christian M. Ringle, and Marko Sarstedt. A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM). SAGE, Los Angeles, third edition edition, 2022. ISBN 978-1-5443-9640-8.

Sven Hauff, Nicole F. Richter, and Christian M. Ringle. Human resource management systems research – how to gain impactful insights through formative measurement and hierarchical component models. The International Journal of Human Resource Management, 36(4):611–635, February 2025. ISSN 0958-5192, 1466-4399. doi: 10.1080/09585192.2025.2464668. URL <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/09585192.2025.2464668>.

Massoomeh Hedayati Marzbali, Aldrin Abdullah, Mohammad Javad Maghsoodi Tilaki, and Mina Safizadeh. HPTED In Residential Settings: A Review Of The Literature. December 2019.

Erin Hoare, Karen Milton, Charlie Foster, and Steven Allender. The associations between sedentary behaviour and mental health among adolescents: a systematic review. Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act, 13(1):108, December 2016. ISSN 1479-5868. doi: 10.1186/s12966-016-0432-4. URL <http://ijbnpa.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12966-016-0432-4>.

Huanchun Huang, Zefeng Lu, Xinmei Fan, Wei Zhai, Linchun Zhang, Di Xu, Zhifeng Liu, Yong Li, Xinyue Ye, Haoming Qin, Kevin Lanza, and Yun Hang. Urban heatwave, green spaces, and mental health: A review based on environmental health risk assessment framework. Science of The Total Environment, 948:174816, October 2024. ISSN 00489697. doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.174816. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0048969724049659>.

Ray C. Jeffery. Crime prevention through environmental design. Sage Publ, Beverly Hills, Calif., 1. print edition, 1971. ISBN 978-0-8039-0086-8.

Rachel Jewett, Catherine M. Sabiston, Jennifer Brunet, Erin K. O’Loughlin, Tanya Scarapicchia, and Jennifer O’Loughlin. School Sport Participation During Adolescence and Mental Health in Early Adulthood. Journal of Adolescent Health, 55(5):640–644, November 2014. ISSN 1054139X. doi: 10.1016/j.jadohealth.2014.04.018. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1054139X14001967>.

- Emil E. Jonescu, Chamil Erik Ramanayaka, Oluwole A. Olatunji, and Talia J. Uylaki. Understanding the impact of urban heat islands on crime: insights from temperature, population density, and green canopy cover. *Crime Sci*, 13(1):15, June 2024. ISSN 2193-7680. doi: 10.1186/s40163-024-00214-w. URL <https://crimesciencejournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s40163-024-00214-w>.
- Anna Karaan, Yana Antonenko, Amaya Celaya Alvarez, Sozvin Al Youssef, Esteban Leon, Matthias Braubach, and Sinaia Netanyahu. Review of indicator frameworks supporting urban planning for resilience and health. *Cities & Health*, 8(5):885–898, September 2024. ISSN 2374-8834, 2374-8842. doi: 10.1080/23748834.2024.2383049. URL <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/23748834.2024.2383049>.
- Stephen R. Kellert, Judith Heerwagen, and Martin Mador, editors. *Biophilic design: the theory, science, and practice of bringing buildings to life*. Wiley, Hoboken, N.J, 2008. ISBN 978-0-470-16334-4.
- Jennifer Kent and Andrew Wheeler. What can Built Environment and Health Professionals Learn from Crime Prevention in Planning? Introducing HPTED’. *Urban Policy and Research*, 34(1):39–54, January 2016. ISSN 0811-1146, 1476-7244. doi: 10.1080/08111146.2015.1034852. URL <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/08111146.2015.1034852>.
- Soheila Khalili, Prashant Kumar, and Laurence Jones. Evaluating the benefits of urban green infrastructure: Methods, indicators, and gaps. *Heliyon*, 10(19):e38446, October 2024. ISSN 24058440. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e38446. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S2405844024144775>.
- Etienne G Krug, James A Mercy, Linda L Dahlberg, and Anthony B Zwi. The world report on violence and health. *The Lancet*, 360(9339): 1083–1088, October 2002. ISSN 01406736. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(02)11133-0. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0140673602111330>.
- Yaxin Lan and Lei Jin. Assessing health lifestyles in contemporary China: Patterns, transitions, and socioeconomic antecedents. *Global Public Health*, 20(1):2447792, December 2025. ISSN 1744-1692, 1744-1706. doi: 10.1080/17441692.2024.2447792. URL <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/17441692.2024.2447792>.

- Jae Lee, Sungjin Park, and Sanghoon Jung. Effect of Crime Prevention through Environmental Design (CPTED) Measures on Active Living and Fear of Crime. *Sustainability*, 8(9):872, August 2016. ISSN 2071-1050. doi: 10.3390/su8090872. URL <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/8/9/872>.
- Venurs H. Y. Loh, Jenny Veitch, Jo Salmon, Ester Cerin, Lukar Thornton, Suzanne Mavoa, Karen Villanueva, and Anna Timperio. Built environment and physical activity among adolescents: the moderating effects of neighborhood safety and social support. *Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act*, 16(1):132, December 2019. ISSN 1479-5868. doi: 10.1186/s12966-019-0898-y. URL <https://ijbnpa.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12966-019-0898-y>.
- Molly Magill. Moderators and mediators in social work research: Toward a more ecologically valid evidence base for practice. *Journal of Social Work*, 11(4):387–401, October 2011. ISSN 1468-0173, 1741-296X. doi: 10.1177/1468017310379930. URL <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/1468017310379930>.
- George A. Marcoulides, editor. *Modern methods for business research*. Quantitative methodology series. Psychology Press, New York, 2013. ISBN 978-1-4106-0438-5 978-1-135-68408-2 978-1-135-68412-9 978-1-135-68413-6. doi: 10.4324/9781410604385.
- Komodo Matta, Vivian Viallon, Edoardo Botteri, Giulia Peveri, Christina Dahm, Anne Ostergaard Nannsen, Anja Olsen, Anne Tjonneland, Alexis Elbaz, Fanny Artaud, Chloe Marques, Rudolf Kaaks, Verena Katzke, Matthias B. Schulze, Erand Llanaj, Giovanna Masala, Valeria Pala, Salvatore Panico, Rosario Tumino, Fulvio Ricceri, Jeroen W. G. Derksen, Therese Haugdahl Nost, Torkjel M. Sandanger, Kristin Benjaminson Borch, J. Ramon Quiros, Carlota Castro-Espin, Maria-Jose Sanchez, Amaia Aizpurua Atxega, Lluís Cirera, Marcela Guevara, Jonas Manjer, Sandar Tin Tin, Alicia Heath, Mathilde Touvier, Marcel Goldberg, Elisabete Weiderpass, Marc J. Gunter, Heinz Freisling, Elio Riboli, and Pietro Ferrari. Healthy lifestyle change and all-cause and cancer mortality in the European Prospective Investigation into Cancer and Nutrition cohort. *BMC Med*, 22(1):210, May 2024. ISSN 1741-7015. doi: 10.1186/s12916-024-03362-7. URL <https://bmcmmedicine.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12916-024-03362-7>.
- Kate Matthews, Timothy Cavagnaro, Philip Weinstein, and Jessica Stanhope. Health by design; optimising our urban environmental micro-

- biomes for human health. *Environmental Research*, 257:119226, September 2024. ISSN 00139351. doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2024.119226. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0013935124011319>.
- Marcio De Almeida Mendes, Inacio Crochemore Mohnsam Da Silva, Pedro Curi Hallal, and Elaine Tomasi. Physical Activity and Perceived Insecurity from Crime in Adults: A Population-Based Study. *PLoS ONE*, 9(9):e108136, September 2014. ISSN 1932-6203. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0108136. URL <https://dx.plos.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0108136>.
- Mateja Mihinjac and Gregory Saville. Third-Generation Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED). *Social Sciences*, 8(6):182, June 2019. ISSN 2076-0760. doi: 10.3390/socsci8060182. URL <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-0760/8/6/182>.
- Hasan Momeni and Ahmad Irankhah. In which areas of Tehran do more crimes occur? Technical report, 2020. News Code: 993003.
- S. Ali Montazeri. Redesigning the residential town in order to improve the health of the residents with an emphasis on physical activity using the HPTED approach, (Case study: Sajjadih town of Tehran), 2019.
- Amanda Kay Montoya. Moderation analysis in two-instance repeated measures designs: Probing methods and multiple moderator models. *Behav Res*, 51(1):61–82, February 2019. ISSN 1554-3528. doi: 10.3758/s13428-018-1088-6. URL <http://link.springer.com/10.3758/s13428-018-1088-6>.
- Mohsen Moradi and Aida Miralmasi. Analysis Academy. URL <https://analysisacademy.com/>.
- Emilio Moyano-Diaz and Rodolfo Mendoza-Llanos. Membership, Neighborhood Social Identification, Well-Being, and Health for the Elderly in Chile. *Front. Psychol.*, 11:608482, January 2021. ISSN 1664-1078. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.608482. URL <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.608482/full>.
- Oliver T Mytton, Nick Townsend, Harry Rutter, and Charlie Foster. Green space and physical activity: An observational study using Health Survey for England data. *Health & Place*, 18(5):1034–1041, September 2012. ISSN 13538292. doi: 10.1016/j.healthplace.2012.06.003. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1353829212001104>.

- NUMBEO. Crime Index by City 2025 Mid-Year. Technical report, 2025. URL <https://www.numbeo.com/crime/rankings.jsp>.
- Statistical Centre of Iran. Statistical Centre of Iran, Yearbook 1400, (2021), Department of judicial statistics, 2021. URL <https://www.amar.org.ir>.
- Eghtesad online. Per capita urban green space in 22 districts of the capital, December 2019. URL <https://www.eghtesadonline.com/photo/398529>. Publisher: Eghtesad Online Section: City.
- Neville Owen, Geneviève N. Healy, Charles E. Matthews, and David W. Dunstan. Too Much Sitting: The Population Health Science of Sedentary Behavior. *Exercise and Sport Sciences Reviews*, 38(3):105–113, July 2010. ISSN 0091-6331. doi: 10.1097/JES.0b013e3181e373a2. URL <https://journals.lww.com/00003677-201007000-00003>.
- George Owusu, Charlotte Wrigley-Asante, Martin Oteng-Ababio, and Adobebea Yaa Owusu. Crime prevention through environmental design (CPTED) and built-environmental manifestations in Accra and Kumasi, Ghana. *Crime Prev Community Saf*, 17(4):249–269, November 2015. ISSN 1460-3780, 1743-4629. doi: 10.1057/cpcs.2015.8. URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1057/cpcs.2015.8>.
- Stephanie A. Prince, Aganeta Enns, Justin J. Lang, Samantha Lancione, Margaret De Groh, and Robert Geneau. Built Environment and Physical Activity Evidence Gaps: A Content Analysis of Published Systematic Reviews. *Int. Journal of Com. WB*, 8(3):797–831, September 2025. ISSN 2524-5295, 2524-5309. doi: 10.1007/s42413-025-00263-2. URL <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s42413-025-00263-2>.
- Andrew K. Przybylski and Netta Weinstein. A Large-Scale Test of the Goldilocks Hypothesis: Quantifying the Relations Between Digital-Screen Use and the Mental Well-Being of Adolescents. *Psychol Sci*, 28(2):204–215, February 2017. ISSN 0956-7976, 1467-9280. doi: 10.1177/0956797616678438. URL <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/0956797616678438>.
- Andrew Putman, Irmina Klicnik, and Shilpa Dogra. Neighbourhood greenness moderates the association between physical activity and geriatric-relevant health outcomes: an analysis of the CLSA. *BMC Geriatr*, 23(1):317, May 2023. ISSN 1471-2318. doi: 10.1186/s12877-023-03997-w. URL <https://bmcgeriatr.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12877-023-03997-w>.

- Polina Putrik, Ludovic Van Amelsvoort, Suhreta Mujakovic, Anton E. Kunst, Hans Van Oers, IJmert Kant, Maria W. Jansen, and Nanne K. De Vries. Assessing the role of criminality in neighbourhood safety feelings and self-reported health: results from a cross-sectional study in a Dutch municipality. BMC Public Health, 19(1):920, December 2019. ISSN 1471-2458. doi: 10.1186/s12889-019-7197-z. URL <https://bmcpublihealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12889-019-7197-z>.
- Bo Qin, Tian Tian, Wangsheng Dou, Hao Wu, and Meizhu Hao. The Association Between the Built Environment and Insufficient Physical Activity Risk Among Older Adults in China: Urban–Rural Differences and Non-Linear Effects. Sustainability, 17(9):4035, April 2025. ISSN 2071-1050. doi: 10.3390/su17094035. URL <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/17/9/4035>.
- Martin Refisch, Karin Kurz, and Jorg Hartmann. Urban Green Space Usage and Life Satisfaction During the Covid-19 Pandemic. Applied Research Quality Life, 19(3):1139–1171, June 2024. ISSN 1871-2584, 1871-2576. doi: 10.1007/s11482-024-10279-z. URL <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s11482-024-10279-z>.
- Andrea S. Richardson, Wendy M. Troxel, Madhumita Ghosh-Dastidar, Gerald P. Hunter, Robin Beckman, Natalie Colabianchi, Rebecca L. Collins, and Tamara Dubowitz. Pathways through which higher neighborhood crime is longitudinally associated with greater body mass index. Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act, 14(1):155, December 2017. ISSN 1479-5868. doi: 10.1186/s12966-017-0611-y. URL <https://ijbnpa.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12966-017-0611-y>.
- Sheryl L. Rifas-Shiman, Li Yi, Izzuddin M. Aris, Pi-I Debby Lin, Marie-France Hivert, Jorge E. Chavarro, Esra Suel, Peter James, and Emily Oken. Associations of street-view greenspace exposure with cardiovascular health (Life’s Essential 8) among women in midlife. Biol Sex Differ, 16(1):45, July 2025. ISSN 2042-6410. doi: 10.1186/s13293-025-00718-3. URL <https://bsd.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13293-025-00718-3>.
- Alessandro Rigolon, Matthew H. E. M. Browning, Olivia McAnirlin, and Hyunseo (Violet) Yoon. Green Space and Health Equity: A Systematic Review on the Potential of Green Space to Reduce Health Disparities. IJERPH, 18(5):2563, March 2021. ISSN 1660-4601. doi: 10.3390/ijerph18052563. URL <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/18/5/2563>.

- Ellen Roemer, Florian Schuberth, and Jorg Henseler. HTMT2—an improved criterion for assessing discriminant validity in structural equation modeling. *IMDS*, 121(12):2637–2650, November 2021. ISSN 0263-5577. doi: 10.1108/IMDS-02-2021-0082. URL <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/IMDS-02-2021-0082/full/html>.
- Annemarie Ruijsbroek, Mariel Droomers, Wim Hardyns, Peter P. Groenewegen, and Karien Stronks. The interplay between neighbourhood characteristics: The health impact of changes in social cohesion, disorder and unsafety feelings. *Health & Place*, 39:1–8, May 2016. ISSN 13538292. doi: 10.1016/j.healthplace.2016.02.001. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S135382921600023X>.
- Annemarie Ruijsbroek, Sigrid M. Mohnen, Mariel Droomers, Hanneke Kruize, Christopher Gidlow, Regina Grazuleviciene, Sandra Andrusaityte, Jolanda Maas, Mark J. Nieuwenhuijsen, Margarita Triguero-Mas, Daniel Masterson, Naomi Ellis, Elise Van Kempen, Wim Hardyns, Karien Stronks, and Peter P. Groenewegen. Neighbourhood green space, social environment and mental health: an examination in four European cities. *Int J Public Health*, 62(6):657–667, July 2017. ISSN 1661-8556, 1661-8564. doi: 10.1007/s00038-017-0963-8. URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00038-017-0963-8>.
- Laney A. Rupp, Shaun Bhatia, Daniel B. Lee, Rachel Wyatt, Gregory Bushman, Thomas A. Wyatt, Jesenia M. Pizarro, Caroline Wixom, Marc A. Zimmerman, and Thomas M. Reischl. Community-engaged crime prevention through environmental design and reductions in violent and firearm crime. *American J of Comm Psychol*, 76(1-2):94–109, September 2025. ISSN 0091-0562, 1573-2770. doi: 10.1002/ajcp.12802. URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/ajcp.12802>.
- Alessio Russo. Urban Green Spaces and Healthy Living: A Landscape Architecture Perspective. *Urban Science*, 8(4):213, November 2024. ISSN 2413-8851. doi: 10.3390/urbansci8040213. URL <https://www.mdpi.com/2413-8851/8/4/213>.
- James F. Sallis, Robert B. Cervero, William Ascher, Karla A. Henderson, M. Katherine Kraft, and Jacqueline Kerr. AN ECOLOGICAL APPROACH TO CREATING ACTIVE LIVING COMMUNITIES. *Annu. Rev. Public Health*, 27(1):297–322, April 2006. ISSN 0163-7525, 1545-2093. doi: 10.1146/annurev.publhealth.27.021405.102100. URL <https://www.annualreviews.org/doi/10.1146/annurev.publhealth.27.021405.102100>.

- Andrea Salmi, Jerome Chenal, and Remi Jaligot. How healthy is the built environment? Challenges and paradigms for measuring urban health. Cities & Health, 8(6):1120–1133, November 2024. ISSN 2374-8834, 2374-8842. doi: 10.1080/23748834.2024.2315807. URL <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/23748834.2024.2315807>.
- Robert J. Sampson. The neighborhood context of well-being. Perspect Biol Med, 46(3 Suppl):S53–64, 2003. ISSN 0031-5982.
- Marko Sarstedt, Christian M. Ringle, and Joseph F. Hair. Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling. In Christian Homburg, Martin Klarmann, and Arnd Vomberg, editors, Handbook of Market Research, pages 1–40. Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2017. ISBN 978-3-319-05542-8. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-05542-8_15-1. URL http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-319-05542-8_15-1.
- Greg Saville and Gerry Cleveland. 2nd generation CPTED: an antidote to the social Y2K virus of urban design. 1997. 2nd Annual International CPTED Conference, Orlando, FL.
- Ana Paula Seraphim, Haifeng Niu, Paulo Morgado, Bruno Miranda, and Elisabete A. Silva. Mapping urban health policies: A scoping review of environmental, behavioural and socioeconomic determinants of health. Progress in Planning, 193:100926, March 2025. ISSN 03059006. doi: 10.1016/j.progress.2024.100926. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0305900624000849>.
- Chongyan Shi, Jin Yan, Lei Wang, and Hejun Shen. Exploring the self-reported physical fitness and self-rated health, mental health disorders, and body satisfaction among Chinese adolescents: A cross-sectional study. Front. Psychol., 13:1003231, September 2022. ISSN 1664-1078. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1003231. URL <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1003231/full>.
- Chelsea R. Singleton, Fikriyah Winata, Kaustubh V. Parab, Oluwafikayo S. Adeyemi, and Susan Aguinaga. Violent Crime, Physical Inactivity, and Obesity: Examining Spatial Relationships by Racial/Ethnic Composition of Community Residents. J Urban Health, 100(2):279–289, April 2023. ISSN 1099-3460, 1468-2869. doi: 10.1007/s11524-023-00716-z. URL <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s11524-023-00716-z>.
- Yiling Song, Mingzhong Zhou, Jiale Tan, Jiali Cheng, Yangyang Wang, Xiaolu Feng, and Hongjun Yu. Association between street greenery and physical activity among Chinese older adults in Beijing, China. Sci Rep, 15

- (1):19509, June 2025. ISSN 2045-2322. doi: 10.1038/s41598-025-03050-3. URL <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-025-03050-3>.
- John R. Speakman and Colin Selman. Physical activity and resting metabolic rate. Proc. Nutr. Soc., 62(3):621–634, August 2003. ISSN 0029-6651, 1475-2719. doi: 10.1079/PNS2003282. URL https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/identifier/S0029665103000855/type/journal_article.
- Giulia Squillacioti, Samuele De Petris, Valeria Bellisario, Enrico Corrado Borgogno Mondino, and Roberto Bono. Urban environment and green spaces as factors influencing sedentary behaviour in school-aged children. Urban Forestry & Urban Greening, 88:128081, October 2023. ISSN 16188667. doi: 10.1016/j.ufug.2023.128081. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1618866723002522>.
- N. E.H. Stappers, M. P.M. Bekker, M. W.J. Jansen, S. P.J. Kremers, N. K. De Vries, J. Schipperijn, and D. H.H. Van Kann. Effects of major urban redesign on sedentary behavior, physical activity, active transport and health-related quality of life in adults. BMC Public Health, 23(1):1157, June 2023. ISSN 1471-2458. doi: 10.1186/s12889-023-16035-6. URL <https://bmcpublichealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12889-023-16035-6>.
- T Sugiyama, E Leslie, B Giles-Corti, and N Owen. Associations of neighbourhood greenness with physical and mental health: do walking, social coherence and local social interaction explain the relationships? Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health, 62(5):e9–e9, May 2008. ISSN 0143-005X. doi: 10.1136/jech.2007.064287. URL <https://jech.bmj.com/lookup/doi/10.1136/jech.2007.064287>.
- Takemi Sugiyama, Jacinta Francis, Nicholas J. Middleton, Neville Owen, and Billie Giles-Corti. Associations Between Recreational Walking and Attractiveness, Size, and Proximity of Neighborhood Open Spaces. Am J Public Health, 100(9):1752–1757, September 2010. ISSN 0090-0036, 1541-0048. doi: 10.2105/AJPH.2009.182006. URL <https://ajph.aphapublications.org/doi/full/10.2105/AJPH.2009.182006>.
- T Takano, K Nakamura, and M Watanabe. Urban residential environments and senior citizens’ longevity in megacity areas: the importance of walkable green spaces. Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health, 56(12):913–918, December 2002. ISSN 0143005X. doi: 10.1136/jech.56.12.913. URL <https://jech.bmj.com/lookup/doi/10.1136/jech.56.12.913>.

Kosuke Tamura, Steven D. Langerman, Stephanie L. Orstad, Sam J. Neally, Marcus R. Andrews, Joniqua N. Ceasar, Mario Sims, Jae E. Lee, and Tiffany M. Powell-Wiley. Physical activity-mediated associations between perceived neighborhood social environment and depressive symptoms among Jackson Heart Study participants. *Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act*, 17(1):91, December 2020. ISSN 1479-5868. doi: 10.1186/s12966-020-00991-y. URL <https://ijbnpa.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12966-020-00991-y>.

Matilda Van den Bosch. Urban green spaces and health - a review of evidence. Technical report, 2016. URL <http://www.euro.who.int/en/health-topics/environment-and-health/pages/news/news/2016/11/who-report-shows-urban-green-spaces-deliver-multiple-health-benefits>Affiliated with WHO.

Jesús Vega. Constructivist Metaphors and Law's Autonomy in Legal Post-Positivism. In Jose Manuel Aroso Linhares and Manuel Atienza, editors, *Human Dignity and the Autonomy of Law*, volume 7, pages 89–111. Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2022. ISBN 978-3-031-14823-1 978-3-031-14824-8. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-14824-8_6. URL https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-031-14824-8_6. Series Title: Law and Visual Jurisprudence.

Min Wang, Ming Qiu, Mengxuan Chen, Yalan Zhang, Surong Zhang, and Lan Wang. How does urban green space feature influence physical activity diversity in high-density built environment? An on-site observational study. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 62:127129, July 2021. ISSN 16188667. doi: 10.1016/j.ufug.2021.127129. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1618866721001540>.

Yiyu Wang, Bert Steenbergen, Erwin Van Der Krabben, Henk-Jan Kooij, Kevin Raaphorst, and Remco Hoekman. The Impact of the Built Environment and Social Environment on Physical Activity: A Scoping Review. *IJERPH*, 20(12):6189, June 2023. ISSN 1660-4601. doi: 10.3390/ijerph20126189. URL <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/20/12/6189>.

Yu Wen, Hong Qi, Tao Long, and Xinjia Zhang. Designed for safety: characteristics and trends in crime prevention through environmental design research. *Journal of Asian Architecture and Building Engineering*, 24(4):3108–3126, July 2025. ISSN 1346-7581, 1347-2852. doi: 10.1080/13467581.2024.2366823. URL <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/13467581.2024.2366823>.

- WHO. *Violence prevention: the evidence*. 2010. ISBN 978-92-4-150084-5. URL <https://iris.who.int/handle/10665/77936>.
- Erik Woody. An SEM Perspective on Evaluating Mediation: What Every Clinical Researcher Needs to Know. *Journal of Experimental Psychopathology*, 2(2):210–251, May 2011. ISSN 2043-8087, 2043-8087. doi: 10.5127/jep.010410. URL <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.5127/jep.010410>.
- Erli Zeng, Yu Dong, Li Yan, and Alin Lin. Perceived Safety in the Neighborhood: Exploring the Role of Built Environment, Social Factors, Physical Activity and Multiple Pathways of Influence. *Buildings*, 13(1):2, December 2022. ISSN 2075-5309. doi: 10.3390/buildings13010002. URL <https://www.mdpi.com/2075-5309/13/1/2>.
- Lin Zhang, Suhong Zhou, Mei-Po Kwan, Fei Chen, and Rongping Lin. Impacts of Individual Daily Greenspace Exposure on Health Based on Individual Activity Space and Structural Equation Modeling. *IJERPH*, 15(10):2323, October 2018. ISSN 1660-4601. doi: 10.3390/ijerph15102323. URL <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/15/10/2323>.
- Yufang Zhang, Marijke Koene, Chen Chen, Cor Wagenaar, and Sijmen A. Reijneveld. Associations between the built environment and physical activity in children, adults and older people: A narrative review of reviews. *Preventive Medicine*, 180:107856, March 2024. ISSN 00917435. doi: 10.1016/j.ypmed.2024.107856. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0091743524000112>.
- Jingjing Zhong, Wenting Liu, Buqing Niu, Xiongbin Lin, and Yanhua Deng. Role of Built Environments on Physical Activity and Health Promotion: A Review and Policy Insights. *Front. Public Health*, 10:950348, July 2022. ISSN 2296-2565. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2022.950348. URL <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpubh.2022.950348/full>.
- Jian Zhu, Yi Yang, Yanmin Zhao, Guoyang Qin, and Xin Su. Using structural equation modeling to examine correlations between health-related physical fitness and cell health among Chinese college students. *BMC Public Health*, 24(1):1557, June 2024. ISSN 1471-2458. doi: 10.1186/s12889-024-19067-8. URL <https://bmcpublichealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12889-024-19067-8>.
- Mengjun Zhu, Xingan Yao, and Abu Talib Mansor. The Chinese version of Selection, Optimization, and Compensation Questionnaire: psychometric properties among adolescent students. *Front. Psychol.*, 16:1453882,

February 2025. ISSN 1664-1078. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2025.1453882.
URL <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2025.1453882/full>.